

Structural Equation Model on Job Performance Among Personnel of Hotels in Caraga Region

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Abstract: The purpose of this quantitative research was to determine the best fit model on job performance of hotel personnel in the context of: organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management in relation to endogenous variable –hotel personnel job performance. The study employed a non-experimental research design utilizing Structural Equation Model (SEM) in finding the best fit model. The data were collected using an adapted survey questionnaire to 400 hotel personnel in CARAGA Region. The results revealed that organizational citizenship behavior and human resource management have significant relationship with job performance. Further, the result showed that Structural Model 4 was the best fit model for job performance. The model indicated that all identified exogenous variables, the organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management were key predictors of hotel personnel job performance.

Keywords: doctor in business administration, organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility, human resource management, job performance, SEM, Philippines

I. Introduction

Over time, the nature of work has evolved. Cross (2017) points out that employment in many parts of the world has changed from primarily physical labor to increasingly service-oriented work in the past hundred years. The change has meant that roles have become more ambiguous, nebulous and hard to define. Through implication, it has become increasingly difficult to articulate what is required of the workers and what is competitive performance. It has become more difficult to assess and distinguish between high performing and low performing workers along these same lines. Managers often believe that performing a mission publicly despite possessing inadequate skills endangers the reputation of their service and can demean and shame workers for their poor performance (Adnan, Rahman & Ahmad, 2018). Until properly trained and motivated workers, usually companies cannot have a large volume of performance (Ukandu&Ukpere, 2014).

The most important element for each company is the performance of the employee because an establishment's success or failure relies on the employee's performance. Some organization personnel leaders evaluate the output of staff members annually or periodically to help them understand suggested opportunities for improvement (Ahmed, 2014). The business that gains the benefit of its talents over other rivals will take the lead in the industry. Employee performance at various jobs is needed for the unit's success (Jayaweera, 2015). Management must understand the importance of employee performance, so that it can take steps to improve and encourage workers to perform well.

In relation to job performance, Poncheri (2006) described organizational citizenship behavior as behaviors that have positive impression on the productivity of organizations through enhanced employee performance. In addition, corporate social responsibility (CSR) practices have been shown to have a positive impact towards employee attitudes and behaviors, which are considered important internal stakeholders (Kim, Lee, Lee & Kim, 2010). CSR practices

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increase employee engagement and productivity, and improve retention rates (Park & Levy, 2014). In addition, Boxall and Purcell (2011) argue that the management of human resources ultimately leads to the organization's work performance of employees. Employee work performance quality is dependent on skill, motivation, and incentive function.

Previous studies of performance-related factors have explored the functions of organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management in different types of organizations. However, there are limited studies that have been conducted that examined how far organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management have contributed to the success of the hospitality industry. Henceforth, it is on this note that the researcher was interested to dwell and conduct assessment on matters relating to hotel employee's job performance in CARAGA Region incorporating the relevance of the three variables as construct, namely: organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management.

1.1 Research Objectives

This study focused on the job performance among personnel of hotels in CARAGA Region. It also seek to assess the level of organizational citizenship behavior of hotel employees, measure the level of corporate social responsibility awareness of hotel employees, assess the level of human resource management participation of hotel employees, evaluate the level of job performance of hotel employees , determine the relationship of organizational citizenship behavior and job performance, corporate social responsibility and job performance, human resource management and job performance and determine the best fit model for the hotel employees' job performance in Caraga region.

1.2 Hypotheses

This study tested the following null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance: there is no significant relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and job performance, corporate social responsibility and job performance, human resource management and job performance and there is no model that best fits job performance of hotel employees in Caraga Region.

1.3 Significance of the Study

This study provides an information on the level of job performance, organization citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management among hotel personnel's in region XIII.

In addition, hotels that have the advantage to surpass and increase market share and the success of their workers are a significant part of the modern corporate world particularly in the hospitality industry. This advantage is created by empowering workers of today's pioneering hotel services to become accountable for their jobs, make decisions, and manage their own life at work. There is no sense in underestimating the value of work performance in the workplace: it builds trust between individuals and groups, allowing it more productive and effective to function. If people trust and are more willing to identify challenges and recommend ways to improve the quantity and quality of the output, the organization will be even better served.

Specifically, this study will substantially contribute to the hotel administrators' especially human resource management division on forming policies, programs and projects that will empower its employees leading a more productive working environment and an empowered organization. Also, this study will help in all level and position of the personnel to work more for their personal growth and development through perceiving organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management as dimensions of employee performance to become more engaged, empowered and productive. Effective employee job performance not only has positive implications for employee satisfaction, but also many other organizational facets.

II. Method

2.1 Research Design

This study employed a quantitative research design utilizing the descriptive-correlation technique and structural equation model to generate the best-fit-model. Descriptive-correlation research design is used to explain the subject phenomenon and to articulate what variables, conditions and attributes were present (Abbott & McKinney,

2013). Moreover, this kind of research is concerned with how or what exists is related to some preceding event that has influenced or affected a present condition or event (Johnson, 2001). Specifically, this study utilized a correlational research approach since the study seeks to establish the relationship of organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management towards job performance of the hotel employees situated in CARAGA Region.

The study also utilized structural equation modelling to extract the best fit model for job performance. Structural Equation Modelling is a mathematical way of defining the cause and effect of the combined theories of the variables. It is an effective way of constructing and evaluating concept templates. SEM also describes the interaction between different variables directly and indirectly. Therefore, SEM describes a multivariate statistical approach that is able to model by incorporating interaction between the anticipated systems, system calculation errors and the connections between errors. The simultaneous equivalent or multivariate form of regression is also known as SEM (Bollen, 1989; Fox, 2006; Kline, 1998; Lomax&Schumacker, 2004). However, SEM is more reliable than several analytical methods, such as multiple regression, trend analysis, factor analyzes, time series analysis and covariance analyses.

Similarly, Kline (2015) describes structural equation model as a family of interrelated processes. Among its characteristics is the distinction between the latent and observed variables, this allows the researcher to explore and hypothesized various models. In this study the hypothesized models illustrate how the different latent exogenous variables relate with the latent endogenous variable and its indicators. As proposed by Kline (2015), there are six essential steps in structural equation modelling; 1) specifying the model; 2) determining whether the model is theoretically plausible; 3) choosing measures for the variables identified in the model; 4) estimating the model using a computer program; 5) updating and evaluating the model if needed; and 6) analyzing accurately and comprehensively the extracted best fit model through a report.

2.2 Population and Sample

In order to choose the respondents, scientific process was followed. A selective selection was used to pick the respondents for this analysis. The deliberate choice for the informant is the purposive sampling method because of the characteristics of the informant. The methodology is non-random and does not involve fundamental hypotheses or a certain number of informants. In brief, the researcher determines what is considered to be and recognized individuals, by knowledge or experience who can and are able to provide details (Bernard, 2017; Tongco, 2007).

Around 400 full-time/permanent hotel employees on different administrative and support offices such human resources, finance department, production support and others from the different hotels in CARAGA Region were surveyed. The accurate sample size of the respondents was determined using the Slovin's formula. Such computed after the researcher determined the actual population size of the hotels in CARAGA Region. The data gathering took place during the secondquarter of 2019 until the last quarter of the said year. Bagozzi and Yi (2012) assert for sample above 200 was ideal when using Structural Equation Model (SEM). Moreover, SEM deals with large sample to be more effective and to reduce measurement errors (Hair et al., 2016).

Thus, securing a sample of 400 was justified and appropriate. On the other hand, employees outsource from agency and subcontract were excluded as they cannot truly assess the job performance of employees because of the nature and time consideration of study considers. Accordingly, if at any time the participants do not feel comfortable in accomplishing the questionnaire, they were free to withdraw their participation without negatively impacting their involvement and relationships with the research and the researcher. There were no pressure to those who choose to discontinue to answer the questionnaire and explanations were also not required.

2.3 Research Instrument

Primary data was used in gathering information about the study which consists of four parts, namely: organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility, human resource management and job performance of the hotel employees. The survey questionnaires that utilized in the conduct of the study are from various related researchers. Restructuring will carried out to make the instrument more applicable in the current undertakings and in the local hotel setting. To make the instrument more contemporary, it will be validated by five experts in the field management and even with other field of organizational supervision. After validation, pilot testing will be performed. Cronbach alpha will be used to check the validity of the questionnaire. Cronbach's alpha consistency coefficient customarily ranges between zero to one. The closer the Cronbach's alpha coefficient is to one, the larger the internal constancy of the items in the scale (Gliem&Gliem, 2003). Moreover, Darren and Mallery (1999) postulated the following

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rules of thumb in measuring the reliability of the questionnaire using Cronbach's alpha; if result is greater than or equal to 0.9 it is excellent, greater than or equal to 0.8 is good; greater than or equal to 0.7 is acceptable; greater than or equal to 0.6 is questionable; greater than or equal to 0.5 is poor and greater than or equal to 0.4 is unacceptable.

The survey on organizational citizenship behavior was adapted from the study of Muthuraman and Al-Hazi (2017). The instrument was designed to measure the organizational citizenship behavior as perceived by hotel employees based on five factors, namely: altruism, conscientiousness, civic virtue, sportsmanship and courtesy.

And the survey on corporate social responsibility was adapted from the study of Galbreath, (2008). The instrument was designed to measure the corporate social responsibility as perceived by hotel employees based on four factors, namely: economic, legal, ethical and discretionary.

Also, the survey on human resource management was adapted from the study of Kutanis et al. (2012). The instrument was designed to measure the human resource management as perceived by hotel employees based on three factors, namely: transformative engineering, leadership and workplace learning.

Lastly, the survey on employee job performance was adapted from the study of Munisamy (2013). The instrument was designed to measure the job performance as perceived by hotel employees based on three factors, namely: stress, working environment, workload and salary.

III. Results

Presented in this chapter are the data and deconstruction of findings based on the responses of the respondents on the job performance of personnel of hotels in CARAGA Region. The discussions are sequenced according to the following sub-headings: level of organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility, human resource management participation and level of employee job performance; the relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and job performance, corporate social responsibility and job performance, human resource management participation and job performance. And lastly, the best fit model that predicts job performance of personnel of hotels. It could also be noted that in Tables 1-4 the standard deviation is less than 1.0, which is the typical standard deviation for a 5-point Likert scale. This indicates consistency of response.

3.1 Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Shown in Table 1 is the level of organizational citizenship behavior among hotel personnel. The overall mean score obtained on the organizational citizenship behavior is 4.52, described by the respondents as very high; this means that the overall response of hotel personnel in terms of organizational citizenship behavior is always observed. Specifically, the mean ratings of the indicators of organizational citizenship behavior are elaborated as follows: *altruism* obtained a mean rating of 4.56; *courtesy* attained a 4.54 mean; *conscientiousness* garnered a mean of 4.51; *civic virtue* got a mean of 4.49; *sportsmanship* garnered a mean score of 4.51, where all mean scores are interpreted as very high.

Table 1
Level of Organizational Citizenship Behavior

Items	SD	Mean	D.E.
Altruism	0.257	4.56	Very High
Courtesy	0.291	4.54	Very High
Conscientiousness	0.331	4.51	Very High
Civic Virtue	0.341	4.49	Very High
Sportsmanship	0.301	4.51	Very High
OVERALL	0.220	4.52	Very High

3.2 Corporate Social Responsibility

Depicted in Table 2 is the level of corporate social responsibility of personnel of hotels in CARAGA Region. The overall mean score is 4.22, considered by respondents as very high; this means that the overall response of the personnel among hotels in terms of corporate social responsibility that the specific corporate social responsibility is always observed. Moreover, the mean rating of the indicators of corporate social responsibility are discussed as follows: *economics* has a mean of 4.18 or high; *legal* obtained a mean of 4.24 or very high; *ethical* got a mean score of 4.26 or very high; and *discretionary* acquired a mean of 4.22 or very high.

Table 2
Level of Corporate Social Responsibility

Items	SD	Mean	D.E.
Economic	0.485	4.18	High
Legal	0.501	4.24	Very High
Ethical	0.492	4.26	Very High
Discretionary	0.478	4.22	Very High
OVERALL	0.411	4.22	Very High

3.3 Human Resource Management

Indicated in Table 3 is the summary of the level of human resource management as perceived by personnel of hotels. The overall mean score is 4.51, perceived by the respondents as very high; this means that the overall perception of the personnel of hotels in terms of the human resource is always observed. Additionally, the mean rating of the indicators of human resource management are presented as follows: *transformative engineering* garnered a mean of 4.49 or very high; *leadership* has a mean of 4.50 or very high; and *workplace learning* obtained a mean of 4.54 or very high.

Table 3
Level of Human Resource Management

Items	SD	Mean	D.E.
Transformative Engineering	0.307	4.49	Very High
Leadership	0.297	4.50	Very High
Workplace Learning	0.284	4.54	Very High
OVERALL	0.228	4.51	Very High

3. 4 Job Performance

Presented in Table 4 is the level of job performance of personnel of hotels in CARAGA Region. The overall mean score is 4.47, perceived by respondents as very high; this means that the overall response of personnel of hotels in terms of their job performance is always observed. Furthermore, the mean rating of the indicators of job performance are discussed as follows: *stress* has a mean of 4.34 or very high; *working environment* rounded up a mean of 4.45 or very high; workload garnered a mean score of 4.49 or very high; and *salary* attained a mean of 4.47 or very high.

Table 4
Level of Job Performance

Items	SD	Mean	D.E.
Stress	0.301	4.49	Very High
Working Environment	0.358	4.45	Very High
Workload	0.299	4.49	Very High
Salary	0.272	4.47	Very High
OVERALL	0.241	4.47	Very High

3.5 Correlation between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job Performance

Table 5 exhibits the data results of correlations between organizational citizenship behavior and job performance. The overall r-value attained by the aforesaid measures is 0.493 ($p < 0.05$) hence significant rejecting the null hypothesis of having no significant relationship.

Moreover, it was observed that *stress, working environment, workload and salary* as indicators of job performance were correlated to altruism, the overall r-value is 0.374 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant. When indicators of job performance are correlated to courtesy, the over-all r-value is 0.329 with $p < 0.05$ hence significant. As the indicators of job performance are correlated to role of conscientiousness, it has an r-value of 0.559 with $p < 0.05$, hence it is significant. Also, when indicators of job performance are correlated to civic virtue, it has an r-value of 0.354 with $p < 0.05$, hence it is significant. Lastly, when indicators of job performance are correlated to sportsmanship, it has an r-value of 0.281 with $p < 0.05$, hence it is significant.

Table 5
Correlation between Organizational Citizenship Behavior and Job Performance

Organizational Citizenship Behavior	Job Performance of Hotel Employees				Overall Job Performance of Hotel Employees
	Stress	Working Environment	Workload	Salary	
Altruism	0.353* (0.000)	0.326* (0.000)	0.226* (0.000)	0.259* (0.000)	0.374* (0.000)
Courtesy	0.306* (0.000)	0.267* (0.000)	0.183* (0.000)	0.278* (0.000)	0.329* (0.000)
Conscientiousness	0.416* (0.000)	0.354* (0.000)	0.266* (0.000)	0.327* (0.000)	0.435* (0.000)
Civic Virtue	0.319* (0.000)	0.255* (0.000)	0.253* (0.000)	0.292* (0.000)	0.354* (0.000)
Sportsmanship	0.235* (0.000)	0.237* (0.000)	0.202* (0.000)	0.201* (0.000)	0.281* (0.000)

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Overall Organizational Citizenship Behavior	0.452* (0.000)	0.398* (0.000)	0.315* (0.000)	0.378* (0.000)	0.493* (0.000)
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*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

3.6 Correlation between Corporate Social Responsibility and Job Performance

Table 6 shows the data results of correlations between corporate social responsibility and job performance. The overall r-value obtained from the aforesaid measures is -0.026 with a p-value of less than 0.05 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. The result is not significant, and the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is failed to reject.

Table 6

Correlation between Corporate Social Responsibility and Job Performance

Corporate Social Responsibility	Job Performance of Hotel Employees				
	Stress	Working Environment	Workload	Salary	Overall Job Performance of Hotel Employees
Economic	0.030 (0.554)	-0.013 (0.790)	0.014 (0.774)	0.096 (0.055)	0.036 (0.465)
Legal	-0.058 (0.249)	-0.047 (0.351)	-0.045 (0.364)	0.025 (0.619)	-0.042 (0.398)
Ethical	-0.018 (0.716)	0.008 (0.880)	0.001 (0.978)	0.041 (0.416)	0.009 (0.856)
Discretionary	-0.083 (0.097)	-0.053 (0.288)	-0.136* (0.007)	-0.007 (0.883)	-0.090 (0.073)
Overall Corporate Social Responsibility	-0.038 (0.444)	-0.031 (0.531)	-0.049 (0.032)	0.046 (0.359)	-0.026 (0.609)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

Additionally, it was observed that *stress, working environment, workload and salary* as indicators of job performance when correlated to economic, the overall r-value is 0.036 with $p < 0.05$ hence, not significant. When indicators of job performance are correlated to legal, the over-all r-value is -0.042 with $p < 0.05$, hence not significant. And when indicators of job performance are correlated to ethical, the over-all r-value is 0.009 with $p < 0.05$, hence not significant. And lastly, as the indicators of job performance are correlated to discretionary, it obtained an overall r-value of -0.090 with $p < 0.05$, hence it is also significant. All the probability values showed no significant correlations.

3.7 Correlation between Human Resource Management and Job Performance

Table 7 presents the data results of correlations between human resource management and job performance. The overall r-value obtained from the aforesaid measures is 0.503 with a p-value of less than 0.05 which is lesser than 0.05 level of significance. The result is significant, and the null hypothesis of no significant relationship is rejected.

Furthermore, it was observed that *stress, working environment, workload and salary* as indicators of job performance when correlated to transformative engineering, the overall r-value is 0.293 with $p < 0.05$ hence, significant.

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When indicators of job performance are correlated to leadership, over-all r-value is 0.435 with $p < 0.05$ hence significant. Finally, as the indicators of job performance are correlated to workplace learning, it have an overall r-value of 0.438 with $p < 0.05$, hence it is significant. The probability values showed significant correlations.

Table 7
Correlation between Human Resource Management and Job Performance

Human Resource Management	Job Performance of Hotel Employees				Overall Job Performance of Hotel Employees
	Stress	Working Environment	Workload	Salary	
Transformative Engineering	0.315* (0.000)	0.214* (0.000)	0.186* (0.000)	0.205* (0.000)	0.293* (0.000)
Leadership	0.386* (0.000)	0.341* (0.000)	0.282* (0.000)	0.357* (0.000)	0.435* (0.000)
Workplace Learning	0.434* (0.000)	0.321* (0.000)	0.267* (0.000)	0.360* (0.000)	0.438* (0.000)
Overall Human Resource Management	0.490* (0.000)	0.378* (0.000)	0.317* (0.000)	0.397* (0.000)	0.503* (0.000)

*Significant at 0.05 significance level.

3.8 The Best Fit Model that Predicts Job Performance among Personnel of Hotels

This part analyzes the interrelationships between the research variables. In an effort to achieve the best fit model of job performance, four alternative models were tested. Each model has a structure that could be broken down into two sub-models composed of a model of measurement and a model of structure. The measurement model reflects the latent constructs of the measurement loads on each variable, while the latent variables are defined by the structural model. In addition, fit evaluation is a basis for adopting and rejecting the model. In this model, the researcher generally wanted to identify the interrelationships between the hypothesized models as well as to determine the best-fit model of the job performance among personnel of hotels. When a structured model comes up with an acceptable fit, it indicates the consistency between variables of the empirical interactions as implied by the model.

In terms of the research question associated to the model that best characterizes the variables that predicts job performance among personnel of hotels, the original proposed model outlined in Figure 1-4 requires some modifications in order to fit the data. There were four generated models presented in this study. The summary of findings of the goodness of fit measures of these five generated models shown in Table 8.

All the indices included must continuously fall within acceptable ranges when identifying the best fit model. The value of the chi-square / degrees of freedom should be between 0 and 2, with the corresponding p-value of 0.05 or higher. Root Mean Square of Error Approximation must be less than 0.05 and must be higher than or equal to 0.05 for its respective Pclose value. Other indexes such as the Normed Fit Index, the Tucker-Lewis Index, the Comparative Index and the Fit Index Goodness must all be higher than 0.90.

The first model includes the direct causal relationship of between the exogenous variables: organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management towards the endogenous variable - job performance of the hotel employees. The model was found a poor fit as presented by the CMIN/DF= 1.810 with its p-value=.000 and RAMSEA =.052 with Pclose=.377 as it did not reach the criteria and hence indicate a poor fit.

The second structural considers a model showing correlation of organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility, and human resource management and the direct causal relationship to employee job. But, the

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model was still found non-fitting to the data as indicated by CMIN/DF=2.018, p-value=.000 and RMSEA=.058 with Pclose=0.174.

Table 8
Summary of Goodness of Fit Measures

Model	CMIN/DF 0<value<2	P-Value > .05	NFI > .95	TLI > .95	CFI > .95	GFI > .95	RMSEA < .05	P-Close > .05
1	1.810	0.000	0.917	0.952	0.961	0.932	0.052	0.377
2	2.018	0.000	0.921	0.942	0.958	0.944	0.058	0.174
3	2.122	0.000	0.931	0.944	0.962	0.955	0.061	0.150
4	1.414	0.069	0.960	0.981	0.988	0.974	0.037	0.783

The third structural model showed a model modification showing correlation of exogenous variables and the direct causal relationship to endogenous variable. Model 3 was found still to have indices that indicate a poor fit as indicated specifically CMIN/DF=2.122, p-value=0.000 and RMSEA=.061 with pclose=0.150.

Finally, the fourth structural model depicted a model modification showing interrelationship of exogenous variables and direct causal relationship to endogenous considering its observed variables. The Goodness of Fit Measures of Structural Model 4 presented in Figure 1 depicts a network of interrelationships of the following: organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management towards job performance with its observed variables. In Table 8, the goodness of fit of Model 5 was examined using the following indices: Chi-square/Degree of Freedom (CMIN/DF), Root Mean Square of Error Approximation (RMSEA), Normed Fit Index (NFI), Tucker-Lewis Index (TLI), Comparative Fit Index (CFI)/Goodness of Fit Index (GFI). The criterion for each index indicating a good fit for all outcomes must be in accordance with the requirements shown in Table 8. The results as reflected by CMIN/DF= 1.414, p-value =0.069, NFI = .960, TLI = .981, CFI = .988 , GFI = .974, RMSEA = .037 and Pclose = .783, fall within the indices thus the result signify the best fit model.

Figure 1 shows the structural model 4 generated, of which the direct link between the latent exogenous variables and their direct effect on the latent endogenous variable. The endogenous latent variable in the model is the Job Performance (JPHE) with observed variables namely Stress (STRESS), Working Environment (WE) and Salary (SALARY). There are three exogenous latent variables namely: Organizational Citizenship Behavior (OCB) with two observed variable left which are altruism (ALTT) and Sportsmanship (SPORTS); another exogenous variable Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) with observed variables namely Economic (ECO), Ethical (ETH) and Discretionary (DIS); and Human Resource Management (HRM) which measured by Transformative Engineering (TE) and Workplace Learning (WL).

This model clearly illustrates the importance of organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management to job performance of personnel among hotels in CARAGA Region.

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Those endogenous variables with respect to its observed variables, it play a major role for personnel towards their performance in the hotel. Thus, the findings suggest that the personnel job performance is best anchored on their strong evidence of organizational citizenship behavior, corporate social responsibility and human resource management.

Figure 1. Structural Model 4 in Standardized Solution

LEGEND:

ALT	-	Altruism	ECO	-	Economic
OCB	-	Org. Citizenship Behavior	ETH	-	Ethical
			DIS	-	Discretionary
			CSR	-	Corp. Social Responsibility
TE	-	Transformative Engineering			
WL	-	Workplace Learning	STRESS	-	Stress
HRM	-	Human Resource Management	WORK	-	Workload
			JPHE	-	Job Performance

Conclusion

The following conclusions are taken in light of the research results. This study's results explicitly verify the best predictors of the job performance among hotel personnel. First, the findings exposed that in terms of job performance, of the three exogenous variables, organizational citizenship behavior got the highest total mean. Therefore, it can be determined that, organizational citizenship behavior has an impact in developing a great personnel performance. And

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among all observed variables altruism obtained the highest-level mean score which is also a direct variable of organizational citizenship behavior. It implies that helping colleagues and employees to perform their duties is a good company practice that contributes overall job performance.

The results on the test of the null hypotheses stating that there is no significant relationship between organizational citizenship behavior and human resource management to job performance were rejected while null hypothesis establishing relationship between corporate social responsibility and job performance was accepted. Therefore, result of the study corroborates with the propositions that there is a link between organizational citizenship behavior and job performance (Organ, 2013); there is no association between corporate social responsibility and job performance (Wocke&Merwe, 2007); and that there is a connection between human resource management and job performance (Wilton (2011).

Moreover, the null hypothesis stating that there is no model that best fits job performance among hotel personnel in CARAGA REgion was rejected.

Recommendation

The following recommendations are made in considerations of the results and conclusions of the study. The results concluded that corporate social responsibility seems to have the low mean score. It is recommended that in hospitality industry specifically hotels to create programs and initiatives that will value corporate social responsibility and other forms that the community and stakeholders may benefit. The company may look unto the different context of CSR to maintain good relationship to community and continuance of hotel operation.

In terms of organizational citizenship behavior, it is suggested that employee themselves continue to work hand-in-hand, collaborate always and understand each strengths and weaknesses as individual continues to perform its duties and responsibilities, so that everybody have a contribution in achieving the goals of the company. With human resource management, the department may initiate programs and activities that will enhance and capacitate hotel personnel to perform well and be an asset in the company without sacrificing the benefit, compensation and incentives that personnel needs to have.

Furthermore, it is recommended that hotel personnel and top management may perform a win-win solution in combat of the day to day operation for them to develop traits on organizational citizenship behavior, dynamics of corporate social responsibilities and platforms being upheld by human resource management .is a good start to h business even on a small scale while still in the university. To end up, it is recommended to future researchers to e....., and dwell on the other dimensions and factors of personnel job performance.

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References

- [1] Cross, D.E., 2017. Global Diversity and Organizational Culture's Impact on Adaptation, Performance, and Innovation. In *Organizational Culture and Behavior: Concepts, Methodologies, Tools, and Applications* (pp. 1790-1808). IGI Global.
- [2] Adnan, A.M., Rahman, A.E.A. and Ahmad, R., 2018. Factors Influencing Turnover Intention among Fast Food Restaurant Managers. *Sciences*, 8(17), pp.195-210.
- [3] Ukandu, N.E. and Ukpere, W.I., 2014. factors impacting job satisfaction of employees in the fast food industry in Cape Town. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 5(3), pp.51-51.
- [4] Ahmed, A.A., 2014. *The relationship between human resource management and employee performance among hotels in Langkawi* (Doctoral dissertation, Universiti Utara Malaysia).
- [5] Jayaweera, T. (2015). Impact of work environmental factors on job performance, mediating role of work motivation: a study of hotel sector in England. *International journal of business and management*, 10(3), 271.
- [6] Poncheri, R. M., 2006. The impact of work context on the prediction of job performance.
- [7] Kim, H. R., Lee, M., Lee, H. T., and Kim, N. M., 2010. Corporate social responsibility and employee-company identification. *Journal of Business Ethics*, 95(4), 557-569.
- [8] Park, S. Y., and E. Levy, S., 2014. Corporate social responsibility: perspectives of hotel frontline employees. *International Journal of Contemporary Hospitality Management*, 26(3), 332-348.
- [9] Boxall, P. and Purcell, J., 2011. *Strategy and human resource management*. Macmillan International Higher Education.
- [10] Abbott, M.L. and McKinney, J., 2013. *Understanding and applying research design*. John Wiley & Sons.
- [11] Johnson, B. 2001. Toward a new classification of nonexperimental quantitative research. *Educational Researcher*, 30(2), 3-13.
- [12] Bollen, K.A., 1989, *Structural Equations with Latent Variables*. New York: John Wiley & Sons.
- [13] Fox, J., 2006. Teacher's corner: structural equation modeling with the sem package in R. *Structural equation modeling*, 13(3), 465-486.
- [14] Kline, R.B., 1998. *Principles and Practice of Structural Equation Modeling*. New York: The Guilford Press.
- [15] Lomax, R.G. and Schumacker, R.E., 2004. *A beginner's guide to structural equation modeling*. psychology press.
- [16] Kline, R.B., 2015. *Principles and practice of structural equation modeling*. Guilford publications.
- [17] Bernard, H.R., 2017. *Research methods in anthropology: Qualitative and quantitative approaches*. Rowman& Littlefield.
- [18] Tongco, M.D.C., 2007. Purposive sampling as a tool for informant selection. *Ethnobotany Research and applications*, 5, pp.147-158.
- [19] Bagozzi, R.P. and Yi, Y., 2012. Specification, evaluation, and interpretation of structural equation models. *Journal of the academy of marketing science*, 40(1), pp.8-34.
- [20] Hair Jr, J.F., Hult, G.T.M., Ringle, C. and Sarstedt, M., 2016. *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage publications.

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- [21] Gliem, J. A., and Gliem, R. R., 2003. Calculating, interpreting, and reporting Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient for Likert-type scales. Midwest Research-to-Practice Conference in Adult, Continuing, and Community Education.
- [22] Darren, G., and Mallery, P., 1999. SPSS for windows step by step: A simple guide and reference. Needham Heights, MA: Allyn & Bacon.
- [23] Muthuraman, S., and Al-Haziazi, M., 2017. Examining the Factors of Organizational Citizenship Behaviour with reference to Corporate Sectors in Sultanate of Oman. *International Review of Management and Marketing*, 7(1), 413-422.
- [24] Galbreath, J., 2008. The benefits of corporate social responsibility: An empirical study. In *ANZAM conference proceedings (22nd annual conference)*, Auckland.
- [25] Kutanis, R. O., Mesci, M., Comlekci, I., and Sahin, O., 2012. Investigating hotel employee involvement in strategic human resources management. *Tourism: An International multidisciplinary journal of tourism*, 7(1), 117-134.
- [26] Munisamy, S., 2013. Identifying factors that influence job performance amongst employees in oil palm plantation-FASS Final Project (Psychology).
- [27] Organ, D. W., 2013. Organizational citizenship behavior and the good soldier. In *Personnel selection and classification* (pp. 69-84). Psychology Press.
- [28] Wocke, A., and Merwe, M., 2007. An investigation into responsible tourism practices in the South African hotel industry. *South African Journal of Business Management*, 38(2), 1-15.
- [29] Wilton, N., 2011. The shifting sands of employability. *CESR Review*, 4.